

NDAC/LO/077

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"SIMSET": SIMULATION OF INPUT DATA FOR THE SET SOLUTION

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1. INTRODUCTION

This is a brief description of the software package SIMSET (Version 2) for simulating input data for the Set Solution, and in particular of the second simulation run performed at LO (tape "LOSIM2"). [The first run, "LOSIM1", was mailed to CUO on July 31. That was made with the undocumented and now obsolete Version 1 of SIMSET.]

2. PURPOSE OF SIMULATIONS

The purpose of SIMSET is to provide extensive sets of input data for the Set Solution (or Great Circle Reduction) process, with a high degree of realism at least for the astrometric part of the data. Photometric data are also generated, but the simulation model is here rather simplistic and the data may not be adequate for tests of the IDT Photometry process.

The data are intended to assist testing of

- (i) the RGO/DSRI data interface format (Petersen, 1986 May 6);
- (ii) the construction and solution of normal equations for the geometrical great-circle reduction, including the elimination of slit inconsistencies;
- (iii) methods for dynamical smoothing.

Emphasis is put on the generation of a realistic attitude motion and the rigorous calculation of grid coordinates from this attitude and stellar parameters. The simulated data include an OGAR estimate of the actual attitude, the fractional part of the grid coordinates with random errors, and an approximate version of the stellar catalogue. Furthermore, the 'true' attitude and abscissae are provided as separate files for comparison with the results of the great-circle reduction.

SIMSET can quickly generate sufficiently long data streams (say, 12 hours) *only* because details on the sub-frame level, such as individual IDT samples and the Star Observation Strategy, are completely ignored. Thus it cannot entirely replace test data on the ESOC format filtered through the RGO processing. However, the greater ease and flexibility by which input data can be generated with SIMSET will be needed for more extensive tests.

Shortcomings of the present Version 2, which may be remedied in future versions should the need arise, are for instance:

- (A) that no double or multiple stars are included;
- (B) that minor planets are not included;
- (C) that the data are 'perfect' (no mavericks or similar).

3. SIMULATION MODELS

3.1. Attitude simulation

The 'true' attitude motion is generated in terms of the three Euler angles (ϕ , θ , ψ) relative to the nominal attitude. These are obtained by integrating the equations of motion,

$$\ddot{\phi} = [T_x - (J_{zz} - J_{yy} - J_{xx}) \dot{\Omega} \dot{\theta}] / J_{xx} \quad (1a)$$

$$\ddot{\theta} = [T_y + (J_{zz} - J_{yy} - J_{xx}) \dot{\Omega} \dot{\phi}] / J_{yy} \quad (1b)$$

$$\ddot{\psi} = T_z / J_{zz} \quad (1c)$$

with a time step of one frame (32/15 s). A diagonal inertia tensor is assumed ($J_{xx} = 385.7$, $J_{yy} = 430.8$, $J_{zz} = 354.1$ kg m²) and higher-order terms (products of ϕ , θ , ψ , $\dot{\phi}$, $\dot{\theta}$, $\dot{\psi}$) are neglected. The torque expressed in body coordinates (T_x , T_y , T_z) follows the usual expression (cf. van Leeuwen, 1985 June 28) with trigonometric terms in the spin phase angle (Ω), including gyro torques. In addition, a random gaussian white noise is superposed on each axis to account for non-deterministic and high-frequency perturbations. The magnitude of this random torque (rms value per frame and axis) is specified in the input file. For LOSIM2 it is $1.0 \cdot 10^{-9}$ Nm.

The jets are actuated (in all three axes) if the linearly extrapolated Euler angles exceed the primary limit switches in either axis. These limits are set to 420, 420 and 550 arcsec. The thrusts applied are calculated to

bring the Euler angles to zero in 500 seconds, according to a simplified constant-torque model (the constant torque is taken to be the mean of the current torque and the predicted torque 500 s hence). There are limits imposed on the maximum and minimum thrust around each axis, but without quantization.

It is believed that this model for the true attitude motion is sufficiently realistic for the present purposes. The various approximations introduced will certainly give quite significant bias (or low-frequency errors) with respect to any more sophisticated model. However, the important features such as the frequency and magnitude of rate discontinuities and the continuous variation of the Euler angles and their rates in between jet firings are adequately represented. This can be seen from a plot of ϕ , θ , ψ versus time for 5 consecutive great circles (Fig. 1a-c) and a comparison with corresponding plots e.g. by van Leeuwen (1985 June 28, his Fig. 1.3). The statistics for the length of jet intervals in LOSIM2 are also fairly representative of the expected behaviour:

- mean interval between actuations: 666 s
- minimum interval: 439 s
- maximum interval: 1139 s

The input needed for the Set Solution is however an *estimate* of the attitude not the true motion itself. The OGAR estimate was produced from the above true attitude in two steps. First, a first-order Markov process was added independently to each Euler angle. Such a process is completely determined by its variance and correlation time (the autocorrelation function being an exponential). This serves to simulate the estimation errors due to the SM observations. The variance is thus determined by the accuracy of the SM transits (including catalogue errors) and the correlation time by their frequency. In LOSIM2, the s.d. is 0.1 arcsec and the correlation time 200 s. The second step is then to fit a cubic spline to each Euler angle. This is done independently for each axis and jet interval, i.e. without any continuity conditions over the jet firings. The maximum separation between adjacent knots can be specified (LOSIM2: 100 s). Figure 2 shows an example of the OGAR error as function of time.

The Euler angles for both the true and the OGAR attitude are converted to heliotropic angles using the rigorous transformation (NDAC/LO/043) and stored for subsequent calculations and output.

3.2. Star catalogue simulation

The 'true' stellar parameters (position, proper motions, parallax, radial velocity, magnitude and colour) are generated according to a number of parameters specified in the input file. These include the magnitude distribution function $N(B)$ (number of stars brighter than a certain B magnitude) for the whole sky, the proportion of blue, intermediate, and red stars at each magnitude, the mean distance modulus as function of apparent magnitude, and the dispersion in distance modulus. This allows to simulate a realistic sample of positions and parallaxes uniformly over the sky. To calculate proper motions and radial velocities, space motions are simulated assuming an isotropic velocity distribution minus a constant solar motion.

The stars are generated for the whole sky directly in order of increasing right ascension. However, to save disk space, only stars within a certain belt around the mean z axis are retained. (This sub-catalogue still contains many more stars than are actually 'observed' in the subsequent simulations.) By this arrangement, it is possible to generate many different sets, covering different portions of the sky, but still using exactly the same star catalogue as basis (as long as the seed for the catalogue generation is not changed).

Apart from the 'true' catalogue, a parallel catalogue with suitable errors is constructed. In this *a priori* catalogue, the parallaxes and radial velocities are set to zero, while gaussian errors of specified s.d. are added to the positions and proper motions. The magnitudes and colours in the *a priori* catalogue are the same as in the 'true' catalogue. Both catalogues are stored for the subsequent calculations and output.

3.3. Simulation of frame observations

The true orientation of the instrument triad [x y z] in the equatorial J2000 frame is calculated at each frame mid-time from the true heliotropic attitude. This defines also the two viewing directions f_{-1} , f_1 . The satellitocentric vectors to the sun, earth, and moon are then calculated. The ephemerides for the sun and earth are the usual ones (Lindegren, 1984 June 15 and 8); the moon ephemeris is taken from The Astronomical Almanac for 1986, p D46, with the mean rate of longitude diminished by 1.4 deg/cy to give approximate inertial coordinates (geocentric accuracy ~ 0.3 deg).

The geocentric ephemeris of the satellite is calculated from a fixed, circular orbit. The orbital axis, radius, angular velocity, and right ascension at J1988.0 are given as parameters in the input file. The data used for LOSIM2 correspond to a geostationary position at longitude 12° West and an inclination (relative to N_{2000}) of about 1° .

A check is then made for possible occultation of either field by the earth or moon. The check is done by calculating the field coordinates (w_e, z_e) and (w_m, z_m) for the centre of the earth and moon. An earth occultation occurs if

$$(w_e/wocce)^2 + (z_e/zocce)^2 < 1 \quad (2)$$

where $wocce$, $zocce$ are occultation angles specified in the input file. A corresponding condition applies for moon occultation, but with smaller occultation angles ($woccm$, $zoccm$). If the frame is occulted by the earth or moon, no star observations are produced.

If the frame is not occulted, the whole star catalogue is searched for stars within either field of view. The fields are formally extended by $\pm 157''$ in the w coordinate to include 'partially observable stars'. If more than 10 stars are in the field, observations are generated only for the first 10 stars. Bias is avoided by searching the catalogue backwards on even frames. Accurate field coordinates (w, z) are computed from the true attitude and true stellar parameters, including the effects of gravitational deflection by the sun and earth and the satellitocentric aberration

The grid coordinate at frame mid-time is then calculated using a standard polynomial model with 11 geometric and 6 chromatic coefficients, plus a term representing a sinusoidal rotation of the grid around the optical axis with period equal to the heliotropic period. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} G = & \quad g_{10}w + g_{01}z + g_{20}w^2 + g_{11}wz + g_{02}z^2 + \\ & + (h_{00} + h_{10}w + h_{01}z + h_{20}w^2 + h_{11}wz + h_{02}z^2)f + \\ & + [(c_{00} + c_{10}w + c_{01}z) + (d_{00} + d_{10}w + d_{01}z)f](B-V - 0.5) + \\ & + (c_1 \cos \Omega + s_1 \sin \Omega)z \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where f is the field index and Ω the heliotropic spin phase.

The trigonometric terms were added to permit studying the effects of grid rotation on the abscissa solution (and possibly the observability of the Fourier coefficients c_1, s_1). It should be noted that the 'constant chromaticity' coefficient c_{00} cannot be determined in the set solution, which therefore contains only 5 chromatic coefficients.

'Observation errors' are added to the true grid coordinates from a gaussian distribution with variance

$$\sigma_G^2 = o_1/(I_0\tau) + o_2/(I_0^2\tau) + o_3/\tau + o_4 \quad (4)$$

The constants o_1, o_2, o_3, o_4 are specified in the input file. I_0 is the mean stellar count rate in counts/sample and τ is the observing time per frame in s. Since the star observing strategy is not simulated, a very simple algorithm is used to distribute the total frame time (32/15 s) among the observable stars. The allotted time (τ) is simply proportional to

$$t = 270 + 11 \times 1.5^H \quad (5)$$

where H is the HIPPARCOS magnitude [taken to be = $(B+V)/2$]. t approximates the global target observing time per star according to system requirements.

I_0 and the related photometric parameters

$$\beta_1 = b + I_0, \quad \beta_2 = I_0 M_1 \quad (6)$$

are computed by means of the expressions

$$I_0 = \Delta t 10^{0.4[f \log - H + fc \times (B-V)]} \left[1 + p_{10}w + p_{01}z + p_{20}w^2 + p_{11}wz + p_{02}z^2 + q_{00}f \right] \quad (7)$$

$$M_1 = am_0 + am_1(B-V-0.5) + am_2wf + am_3w^2 \quad (8)$$

with parameters $flog, fc, p_{ij}, q_{00}, am_i$ as given in the input file. Δt is the sample time (1/1200 s), and b the (constant) background count rate. Gaussian errors are added to the theoretical β_1, β_2 according to the approximate covariance derived in NDAC/LO/026.

Other data generated for each star in the frame are the grid coordinate difference between the 3- and 5-parameter fits, the corresponding difference in χ^2 , the mean slot number, and the scanfield indices. The grid coordinate difference is simply taken to be a centred gaussian variable with a standard deviation of $1.5\sigma_G$ (NDAC/LO/038). The $\Delta\chi^2$ is taken from a chi-square distribution with 2 degrees of freedom, as expected for single stars. The mean slot number is taken from a uniform distribution [150, 170] for fully observable stars, while for partially observable stars, it is given by the mid-time of that part of the frame, during which the star is actually inside the FOV. Finally the scanfield indices are computed from the field coordinates at frame mid-time, (w, z), according to the formulae

$$i_w = \text{NINT}(0.5(1 + 168(1 - w/s))) \quad (9a)$$

$$i_z = \text{NINT}(0.5(1 + 46(1 - z/s))) \quad (9b)$$

where $s = \sin 0.45^\circ$. I think that this agrees with the convention proposed by Vaghi (letter of 1985 Nov 12), assuming the nominal transformation between (w, z) and (G, H).

In addition, the Starmapper background estimates and their standard deviations are generated once per frame. The background count rates are generated as functions of the galactic latitudes (adding the contributions from the two viewing directions), plus a sinusoidal variation with Ω . The standard deviations are computed as the square root of (the background count rate divided by the number of samples on which the estimate is based). The parameters of the background variation and the number of samples for the standard deviation are specified in the input file.

4. EXECUTION OF SIMULATIONS

4.1. Operational requirements

The software package consists of two major programs for generating and writing the data (simset and wrgomt), plus three small service programs (outatt, outgc, outstar) which prints a fraction of the data for easy inspection. The programs and all subroutines (with the exception of some tape routines - see below) are written in FORTRAN 77 with the use of some extensions according to MIL-STD-1753 (in particular, the DO ... END DO

loop construction is heavily used). Other deviations from standard FORTRAN are: use of lower-case letters for symbolic names, equivalencing character and integer items, use of an exclamation point to denote end-of-line comments, use of the compiler directive \$EMA for virtual memory (see below) and the use of formal parameters in the run string.

Since standard FORTRAN 77 does not allow full control of tape output, it was found necessary to invoke a few (site specific) C-routines for opening and writing on the tape drive. These routines are exclusively called from the FUNCTION subprogramme 'iblk' in wrgomt. A complete description of the actions performed by these routines is found in the header of that subprogramme. At LO/HP9000, the source file wrgomt.f must be compiled with the '-last' option to include the tape routines. At other sites, the user will normally have to substitute the appropriate routine calls from his own system library for the present calls in 'iblk'.

Error messages from simset and wrgomt are reported on logical unit number 7. This unit number is assigned by PARAMETER statements in the main programs and may have to be changed at another site. (In a UNIX environment, there should be a special unit number for error messages apart from the standard output, thus avoiding redirection by '>'.)

The program simset makes use of some large arrays normally requiring virtual memory. These arrays are collected in the COMMON block 'arrays'. In the HP9000 FORTRAN, this block is explicitly put in virtual memory with the directive '\$EMA /arrays/' near the beginning of the main program. The size of this block depends on the maximum number of stars and frames allowed in the simulation, currently set in a PARAMETER statement to $\text{maxnst} = 6000$, $\text{maxnfr} = 20000$. (This is sufficient for intervals up to 11.85 hours or 5.5 great circles; maxnst could probably be lowered to 4000 for this interval.) With current parameters the size of /arrays/ is

$$160 \times \text{maxnst} + 112 \times \text{maxnfr} = 3.2 \text{ Mb}$$

Three intermediate disk files are generated by simset, containing the attitude data (true and OGAR), the stellar data (true and *a priori*), and the frame data. In simulation LOSIM2, covering 5 great circles (18000 frames) and 3204 stars, the sizes of these files were:

ATTFILE	=	1.20 Mb	[$\propto$ nfr],	CPU	=	8 min	[$\propto$ nfr]
STARFILE	=	0.53 Mb	[$\propto$ nst],	CPU	=	16 min	[const]
GCFILE	=	7.12 Mb	[$\propto$ nfr],	CPU	=	150 min	[$\propto$ nfr]

The approximate CPU time needed to generate each file is also indicated (1 flop = 15 μ s from CUO benchmark test 1986.04.11). The expressions in brackets show how the sizes and times scale with the number of frames (nfr) and stars (nst) generated.

Running simset for a realistic set of (say) 5 great circles thus requires a total disk space of about 15 Mb. The other programs access ATTFILE, STARFILE, and GCFILE one record at a time and do not generate any new files (if output is on tape); they are consequently less demanding.

4.2. Running the programs

All parameters determining the simulated data are given in a special input file. This ASCII files should be edited as required for a specific simulation run. The input file used for LOSIM2 is reproduced as Annex 1 to this note. The meaning of each datum is explained in the preceding commentary, which can hopefully be understood in conjunction with the descriptions in Section 3 above.

The simset program is then run with the command (applicable in UNIX)

```
$ simset INFILE STARFILE ATTFILE GCFILE [OPT] [>OUTSIM]
```

['\$' is the UNIX shell prompt, 'simset' is the name of the compiled program the remaining arguments (in CAPITALS) should be replaced by the actual names of the different files or options. The arguments in brackets are optional (can be left out).] The arguments are:

```
INFILE    = name of the input file
STARFILE  = name of the output file to be created for the stellar data
ATTFILE   = name of the output file to be created for the attitude data
GCFILE    = name of the output file to be created for the grid coordinate
           (frame) data
OPT       = 'x' for extensive reporting on standard output (displays the
           number of stars observed in each frame, occultations etc);
           'z' for contiguous numbering (1, 2, ..., nst without gaps) of
           the stars in the sub-catalogue extracted from the full-sky
           catalogue. Default is that the star gets the same identi-
           fication number in the sub-catalogue as in the full-sky
           catalogue;
           'xz' or 'zx' for extensive reporting and contiguous numbering.
```

OUTSIM = name of the file to which standard output will be directed.
 Default is that the standard output appears on the terminal.

The standard output generated by simset consists of reports on the successful execution of critical tasks, in particular reading the input file and writing each of the three major output files. Summary statistics on the number and intervals of jet firings, the number of earth and moon occultations, and the number of observations per frame are also given. Annex 2 is a reproduction of the standard output for LOSIM2.

The output files STARFILE, ATTFILE, and GCFILE may now be inspected by running the service programs with the commands

```
$ outstar STARFILE [>STAR_EX]
$ outatt  ATTFILE  [>ATT_EX]
$ outgc   GCFILE   [>GC_EX]
```

in which *_EX represent the files to which the standard outputs may be directed. The program outstar produces a listing of the true and *a priori* parameters of the first ten and last ten stars in the generated sub-catalogue. Similarly, outatt lists the true and OGAR attitude of the first and last ten frames, while outgc lists the grid coordinates and related data for the same 20 frames. Annex 3-5 reproduce the first page only of each excerpt file for LOSIM2.

To produce a tape output of the simulations in the agreed format (Petersen, 1986 May 6 with extensions), run the wrgomt program with the command

```
$ wrgomt STARFILE ATTFILE GCFILE OUTFILE [dir] [seq] [>OUTWRG]
```

The argument OUTFILE should be the actual name of the output file or tape drive. For instance, to write on magnetic tape at LO/HP9000, the correct name is OUTFILE = '/dev/rmt9'. However, it is also possible to write to the disk instead of tape (this may be convenient in some cases). In that case, one of the optional arguments 'dir' or 'seq' must be given in the run string, depending on whether the disk files should be direct access or sequential access type. Since wrgomt actually creates four files (see below), their names on the disk will be OUTFILE//N, where N = '1', '2', '3', and '4'. For instance, if OUTFILE = 'asdfg' and option 'dir' is specified, then the following four direct access disk files are generated: 'asdfg1', 'asdfg2', 'asdfg3', and 'asdfg4'.

Whether the results are written on tape or disk, the four files generated in sequence contain the following data types:

file #1: data type = 'COOR' (*a priori* stellar data)

file #2: data type = 'FRAM' (frame data)

file #3: data type = 'TABS' (true abscissae)

file #4: data type = 'TATT' (true attitude)

The formats of the first two data types are as described in 'Specification of input to the Great Circle Reduction program system', issue 1 (Petersen, 1986 May 6). The data types 'ABS' and 'TATT' have been added to allow the results of the set solution to be compared with the *true* abscissae and attitude (the true instrument parameters are given in the input file to simset). Their formats are modelled on 'COOR' and 'FRAM', respectively, and described in Annex 7.

The standard output from wrgomt reports on reading the different input files and writing the four data types. An example from LOSIM2 is given as Annex 6.

Fig. 1a, b: True attitude angles ϕ , θ simulated over five great circles (18000 frame.

Fig. 1c (top): True attitude angle ψ simulated over five great circles
Fig. 2 (bottom): OGAR error in the angle ϕ simulated over one great circle

INPUT FILE FOR SIMULATION OF DATA FOR SET SOLUTION

Format appropriate for 'simset' VERSION 2

Data due to: L Lindegren 1986 July 1, Aug 20

To simulate set input data, edit this file as required and run the simulation program with the UNIX command

\$ simset INFILE STARFILE ATTFILE GCFILE

where INFILE is replaced by the actual name of this file. The simulation results are stored on the files specified by the remaining arguments, viz. STARFILE for the star catalogue, ATTFILE for attitude data, and GCFILE for grid coordinates etc

in the example above. To convert these files to the proper input format on magnetic tape ("RGO tape"), use the program 'urgomat'.

When editing this input file, please note the following:

- (1) Comment lines beginning with an exclamation mark (!) can be inserted anywhere, EXCEPT immediately above a data line.
- (2) The special text lines NOT beginning with an '!' (data headers) must not be changed; these are used as checkpoints by the reading program.
- (3) The number and order of data items must not be changed without a corresponding modification in the subroutine 'infile' of the simset program.
- (4) Free format (list directed input) is used for all data. Violations against (1)-(3) usually produce a message of the form 'STOP (infile block xxxxx)' on the standard error output device, where 'block' is replaced by the name of the relevant COMMON block and 'xxxxx' gives the first six characters of the data header preceding the input line causing the error condition.

TAPE IDENTIFIER

The tape identifier (max 8 characters) will be written on the file label record. It must be enclosed between quotes ('xxx').

tape identifier

'LOSIM2'

INITIALIZATION OF RANDOM NUMBER GENERATORS (COMMON block 'seed')

iseedcat = seed for generation of true and a priori star catalogue
 iseedatt = seed for generation of true and OGAR attitudes
 iseedobs = seed for generation of observational errors

Each of these integers should be in the range 0 to 11470 (approx).

iseedcat iseedatt iseedobs
 2 2 2

PARAMETERS DETERMINING THE STAR CATALOGUE (COMMON block 'catalogue')

reference epoch (approx at mid-mission) [year]:
 1990.0

magnitude and colour distribution:

N(B) = no. of stars brighter than B-magnitude B (B=0 to 14)
 P(B-V) = Percentage stars of colour B-V (= -.25, 0.50, 1.25)

B-magnitude	N(B)	P(-.25)	P(0.50)	P(1.25)
0	0			
1	8	59	28	13
2	27	59	28	13
3	104	59	28	13
4	350	59	28	13
5	1030	59	28	13
6	2800	59	28	13
7	8000	48	35	17
8	21400	37	46	17
9	50800	32	51	17
10	85300	21	52	27
11	103200	10	49	41
12	106800	4	38	58
13	107700	3	41	54
14	107700	5	41	54

distance distribution:

mean distance modulus <5*lg(r/10 pc)> = dm0 + dm1*B
 standard deviation of d.m. = dmsd

dm0 dm1 dmsd
 0.85 0.68 1.80

space velocities:

solar motion in equatorial rectangular coord. = vsun(1:3) [km/s]

(spherical) velocity dispersion = vsd [km/s]
 vsun(1) vsun(2) vsun(3) vsd
 0.6 -17.6 9.4 30

standard deviations of a priori catalogue:
 sdpss = s.d. of positions [arcsec]
 sdpm = s.d. of proper motions [arcsec/year]

sdpss
 1.5 sdpm
 0.03

MISSION PARAMETERS (COMMON block 'mission')

Simulated time interval

tbeg = approx time of first simulated frame in [s] from J1988.0
 tint = approx length of simulated interval in [s]

Restrictions:
 -10540800 < tbeg < 162259200 (from the 'earth' routine)
 2 < tint <= (32/15)*maxtir (see PARAMETER in main program)

tbeg
 30022000 tint
 38400

Geocentric satellite orbit

NOTE: Circular geostationary orbit; longitude 12 deg West

rsat(1:3) = unit vector orbital angular momentum (equatorial J2000)
 ageos = semi-major axis [cm]
 ra0 = right ascension for J1988.0 [rad]
 angvel = angular velocity [rad/s]

rsat(1) rsat(2) rsat(3) ageos ra0 angvel
 .009614889 .014974302 .999841650 42164174 4.6797 7.2921151467d-5

Random perturbation torque

ranper = (white noise) perturbation per frame and axis [Nm]

ranper
 1d-9

PARAMETERS CHARACTERIZING THE OGAR ESTIMATE (COMMON block 'ogar')

sig(1:3) = standard deviation about the X, Y, and Z axis [arcsec]
 tau(1:3) = correlation time of errors about X, Y, Z

dirmax = (approximate) maximum cubic spline interval [cs]
 sig(1) sig(2) sig(3) tau(1) tau(2) tau(3) dmax
 0.1 0.1 0.1 200 200 200 100

PARAMETERS CHARACTERIZING THE INSTRUMENT (COMMON block 'instr')

Main nominal parameters

bangle = nominal basic angle [cdeg]
 wfov = half width of FOV along scan [cdeg]
 zfov = half width of FOV normal to scan [cdeg]

bangle wfov zfov
 58.0 0.45 0.45

True field distortion parameters

The true (smoothed) grid coordinate for a star of colour B-V at field coordinates (w, z) in field f is given by

$$G = \begin{aligned} &g10*w + g01*z + g20*w*w + g11*w*z + g02*z*z + \\ &(h00 + h10*w + h01*z + h20*w*w + h11*w*z + h02*z*z)*f + \\ &(c00 + c10*w + c01*z) + (d00 + d10*w + d01*z)*f + (B-V - 0.5) * \\ &[grotc1*cos(omega) + grotc1*sin(omega)]*z \end{aligned}$$

where f = 1 for precedings, -1 for following FOV.

Thus, gij = distortion (at B-V=0.5) common to both fields;
 hij = differential distortion (at B-V=0.5);
 cij = chromaticity common to both fields;
 dij = differential chromaticity;
 grotc1, grotc1 = Fourier coefficients of the variable grid rotation

g10 g01 g20 g11 g02
 170749.01 -50 0 0 0
 h00 h10 h01 h20 h11 h02
 0 0 0 0 0 0
 c00 c10 c01
 0 0 0
 d00 d10 d01
 0 0 0
 grotc1 grotc1
 0 0

Occultations

! An occultation occurs when the field coordinates (u, z) of the Earth
! or Moon centre satisfy (u/woccc)**2 + (z/zoccc)**2 < 1, where woccc,
! zoccc are the effective semi-axes of the occultation field.

wocce, zocce = semi-axes of the Earth occultation field [deg]
woccm, zoccm = semi-axes of the Moon occultation field [deg]

wocce 20.9 zocce 7.1 zoccm 16.5 zoccm 4.9

True photometric parameters

Mean count rate as function of H-magnitude [hmag = (B+V)/2]
and bmv = B-V:
count rate = dex[0.4*(flog - hmag + fcocoef*bmv)] + backg [Hz]

flog fcocoef backg
17.35 0.23 85

Field variation of count rate:
1 + p10*w + p01*z + p20*w**2 + p11*w*z + p02*z**2 + q00*f

p10 p01 p20 p11 p02 q00
0 0 2700 0 2700 0

Field variation of modulation factor M1:
M1 = am0 + am1*(bmv-0.5) + am2*w*f + am3*w**2

am0 am1 am2 am3
-727 -0.057 -0.4 -25

Parameters for the rms grid coordinate error

variance = o1/(b*tau) + o2/(b*b*tau) + o3/tau + o4 [mas**2]
where b = mean stellar count rate in [counts/sample],
and tau = integration time (per frame) in [s]

o1 o2 o3 o4
95 6.5 .039 5.0

Parameters for the Star Mapper background level and error

Background count rate versus galactic latitude and spin phase:
background (BT) = bgb(1) + bgb(2)*sb**bgb(3) + bgb(4)*(1+cos(omega))
background (VT) = bgv(1) + bgv(2)*sb**bgv(3) + bgv(4)*(1+cos(omega))
in [counts/sample/FOV], where sb = abs(sin(galactic latitude))
and omega = spin phase angle

bgb(1) bgv(1) bgb(2) bgv(2) bgb(3) bgv(3) bgb(4) bgv(4)
2.3 2.3 1.0 1.0 4.0 4.0 0.3 0.3

Standard deviation of background count rate:
s.d. = sqrt((mean count rate) / (nmsam)) [counts/sample]
where nmsam = number of SM samples on which the estimate is based

! nmsam
! 100
!

! END OF INPUT FILE

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File "infile" has been read. Tape identification: LOSIM2

Attitude has been simulated for 18001 frames

Number of frames with jet actuations = 58
 Mean interval between jet actuations = 666. s
 Min. interval between jet actuations = 439. s
 Max. interval between jet actuations = 1139. s

Attitude has been stored on file "attit"

Modified Chebyshev coefficients for geocentric satellite ephemeris:

k	x	y	z	vx	vy
0	-37914195.66	29095080.22	-71312.53	-2122.18	-2764.87
1	-27826794.07	-36253899.86	810436.71	2643.56	-2028.65
2	13871591.77	-10644959.45	26090.97	776.44	1011.58
3	2593215.23	3378548.20	-75525.65	-246.36	189.05
4	-606363.41	465318.90	-1140.50	-33.94	-44.22
5	-66260.46	-86326.87	1929.79	6.29	-4.83
6	10191.61	-7820.97	19.17	.57	.74
7	789.30	1028.33	-22.99	-.07	.06
8	-90.60	69.52	-.17	-.01	-.01
9	-5.46	-7.12	.16	.00	.00

Catalogue data have been generated for 3204 stars

Catalogue data have been stored on file "stars"

Frame data have been written on file "grido"

18001 frames with 72932 observations
 1430 frames were occulted by the Earth
 683 frames were occulted by the Moon
 1856 frames were occulted by the Earth or Moon

Obs per frame ... number of frames

0	182
1	806
2	1761
3	2725
4	3096
5	2725
6	1998
7	1353
8	795
9	439
10	265

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CONTENTS ON FILE stars

=====

Tape identification = LOSIM2
 Number of stars = 3204
 Set mid-time = 30041200.
 Set reference pole =
 -.385438621601 -.385763218669 -.838226585179

First and last 10 stars:

Parameter	true value	a priori
star id	1	1
epoch	63115200.	63115200.
RA [deg]	.047826269	.047805917
Dec [deg]	-23.510273824	-23.509505684
pm ra [as/cy]	2.778929	3.547930
pm dec [as/cy]	-.110470	-.483674
par [mas]	2.5654	.0000
rad vel [m/s]	9525.9	.0
mag H = (B+V)/2	7.797	7.797
colour B-V	.851	.851
star id	2	2
epoch	63115200.	63115200.
RA [deg]	.287477523	.287147089
Dec [deg]	-26.161305320	-26.161917213
pm ra [as/cy]	.097524	-2.087620
pm dec [as/cy]	.438437	1.889978
par [mas]	.3404	.0000
rad vel [m/s]	-35440.2	.0
mag H = (B+V)/2	10.918	10.918
colour B-V	.268	.268
star id	3	3
epoch	63115200.	63115200.
RA [deg]	.301844552	.300900112
Dec [deg]	-25.216637725	-25.216589854
pm ra [as/cy]	.048784	-1.117100
pm dec [as/cy]	-.188321	-.253284
par [mas]	.1774	.0000
rad vel [m/s]	-18409.3	.0
mag H = (B+V)/2	8.451	8.451
colour B-V	-.269	-.269
star id	4	4
epoch	63115200.	63115200.
RA [deg]	.357329584	.357698152
Dec [deg]	-23.821360637	-23.821043408
pm ra [as/cy]	-.002323	-2.268226
pm dec [as/cy]	-.020598	-8.194500
par [mas]	.2021	.0000
rad vel [m/s]	-5225.9	.0
mag H = (B+V)/2	9.922	9.922
colour B-V	.133	.133

Annex 3: Example of standard output from outstar (first page only)

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CONTENTS ON FILE attit
 =====

Tape identification = LOSIM2
 Number of frames = 18001
 Time of first frame = 30022000.096120
 Time of last frame = 30060400.097921

First and last 10 frames:

Parameter	true value	a priori
frame number	1	1
mid-time	30022000.096120	30022000.096120
jet flag	0	0
rev angle [deg]	42.995862165	42.995818254
rev phase [deg]	243.125959973	243.125961175
spinphase [deg]	222.721485731	222.721514405
frame number	2	2
mid-time	30022002.229453	30022002.229453
jet flag	0	0
rev angle [deg]	42.995850066	42.995806379
rev phase [deg]	243.126979579	243.126985848
spinphase [deg]	222.821276170	222.821299620
frame number	3	3
mid-time	30022004.362787	30022004.362787
jet flag	0	0
rev angle [deg]	42.995846691	42.995803170
rev phase [deg]	243.127984854	243.127995570
spinphase [deg]	222.921078160	222.921097037
frame number	4	4
mid-time	30022006.496120	30022006.496120
jet flag	0	0
rev angle [deg]	42.995852088	42.995808679
rev phase [deg]	243.128975849	243.128990416
spinphase [deg]	223.020891662	223.020906590
frame number	5	5
mid-time	30022008.629454	30022008.629454
jet flag	0	0
rev angle [deg]	42.995866304	42.995822958
rev phase [deg]	243.129952614	243.129970461
spinphase [deg]	223.120716637	223.120728214
frame number	6	6
mid-time	30022010.762787	30022010.762787
jet flag	0	0
rev angle [deg]	42.995889387	42.995846057
rev phase [deg]	243.130915201	243.130935780
spinphase [deg]	223.220553047	223.220561846
frame number	7	7
mid-time	30022012.896121	30022012.896121

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CONTENTS ON FILE grids

=====

Tape identification = LOSIM2
 Number of frames = 18001

Modified Chebyshev coefficients for geocentric satellite ephemeris:

k	x	y	z	vx	vy
0	-37914195.66	29095080.22	-71312.53	-2122.18	-2764.87
1	-27826794.07	-36253899.86	810436.71	2643.56	-2028.65
2	13871591.77	-10644959.45	26090.97	776.44	1011.58
3	2593215.23	3378548.20	-75525.65	-246.36	189.05
4	-606363.41	465318.90	-1140.50	-33.94	-44.22
5	-66260.46	-86326.87	1929.79	6.29	-4.83
6	10191.61	-7820.97	19.17	.57	.74
7	789.30	1028.33	-22.99	-.07	.06
8	-90.60	69.52	-.17	-.01	-.01
9	-5.46	-7.12	.16	.00	.00

First and last 10 frames:

FRAME NUMBER	1		
number of stars	3		
SM background and s.d. (B) [c/samp]:		6.092	.247
SM background and s.d. (V) [c/samp]:		5.729	.239

star id, p/f	246	1.
field coord w,z	.002249228042	.006059796757
naosam, mslot	853	155
grid coord, sd	.748655	.005065
fitdif, chidif	.002285	5.51
beta1,2 [c/sam]	4.161612	2.714577

star id, p/f	725	-1.
field coord w,z	.008603174265	.001184072728
naosam, mslot	853	309
grid coord, sd	.926083	.003701
fitdif, chidif	.000450	3.22
beta1,2 [c/sam]	9.076039	6.518401

star id, p/f	734	-1.
field coord w,z	-.007629484538	-.002801775338
naosam, mslot	853	101
grid coord, sd	.409784	.004495
fitdif, chidif	-.009654	2.20
beta1,2 [c/sam]	5.620081	3.769268

FRAME NUMBER	2		
number of stars	2		
SM background and s.d. (B) [c/samp]:		5.469	.234
SM background and s.d. (V) [c/samp]:		5.465	.234

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READING FROM FILE "stars":
 Tape identification = LOSIM2
 Number of stars = 3204
 Set mid-time = 30041200.

 DATA TYPE 'COOR':
 19 blocks have been written on file "/dev/rmt9"

READING FROM FILE "attit":
 Tape identification = LOSIM2
 Number of frames = 18001
 Time interval = 30022000. 30060400.

READING FROM FILE "gridc":
 Tape identification = LOSIM2
 Number of frames = 18001

 DATA TYPE 'FRAM':
 273 blocks have been written on file "/dev/rmt9"

READING FROM FILE "stars":
 Tape identification = LOSIM2
 Number of stars = 3204
 Set mid-time = 30041200.
 Reference pole R.A. = 3.9274117146458547 rad
 Reference pole Dec. = -.9940229973552283 rad

 DATA TYPE 'TABS':
 9 blocks have been written on file "/dev/rmt9"

READING FROM FILE "attit":
 Tape identification = LOSIM2
 Number of frames = 18001
 Time interval = 30022000. 30060400.

 DATA TYPE 'TATT':
 74 blocks have been written on file "/dev/rmt9"

ANNEX 7: Format specifications for data types 'TABS' and 'TATT'

TRUE ABSCISSAE FILE (data type 'TABS')

File header blockFile label record

Word	Off	Len	Description
1	0	4	'NDAC' = general identifier
2	4	4	'TABS' = data type identifier (true abscissae)
3	8	8	tape identifier, e.g. 'LOSIM2 '
5	16	4	processing date = 0 for simulated data
6	20	4	= 3 version number of file label format
7	24	4	= 8 number of words in the file label
8	28	4	= 2048 number of words in a block (max)

True abscissae file header record

Word	Off	Len	Description
9	32	4	= 8 number of words in this header record
10	36	4	= 1 version number
11	40	4	= 5 number of words in an abscissa record
12	44	4	right ascension a [rad] of the RGC pole stored as: $\text{int}(a*2**24)$ where a is in the range 0 to 2π
13	48	4	remaining part ra of right ascension stored as: $\text{nint}(ra*2**24)$ where $ra = a*2**24 - \text{int}(a*2**24)$
14	52	4	declination d [rad] of the RGC pole stored as: $\text{int}(d*2**24)$ where d is in the range 0 to 2π
15	56	4	remaining part rd of declination stored as: $\text{nint}(rd*2**24)$ where $rd = d*2**24 - \text{int}(d*2**24)$
16	60	4	number of abscissa records in the file

(continued)

TRUE ABSCISSAE FILE (continued)

Data blocksBlock header record

Word	Off	Len	Description
1	0	4	= 2 number of words in this block header record
2	4	4	number of records in this block

True abscissa record

Name	Off	Len	Description
IDSTAR	0	4	star identification number
SEPOCH	4	4	epoch of set coordinates in s since 1988.0
TABSC	8	4	true abscissae a [rad] stored as: int(a*2**24) where a is the range 0 to 2 π
	12	4	remaining part ra of abscissa stored as: nint(ra*2**24) where ra = a*2**24 - int(a*2**24)
SINORD	16	4	sine of the ordinate (s) stored as: nint(s*1d9) + 1d9 where s is in the range -1 to 1

TRUE ATTITUDE FILE (data type 'TATT')

File header blockFile label record

Word	Off	Len	Description
1	0	4	'NDAC' = general identifier
2	4	4	'TATT' = data type identifier (true attitude)
3	8	8	tape identifier, e.g. 'LOSIM2 '
5	16	4	processing date = 0 for simulated data
6	20	4	= 3 version number of file label format
7	24	4	= 8 number of words in the file label
8	28	4	= 2048 number of words in a block (max)

(continued)

TRUE ATTITUDE FILE (continued)

True attitude file header record

Word	Off	Len	Description
9	32	4	= 7 number of words in this header record
10	36	4	= 1 version number
11	40	4	= 8 number of words in an attitude record
12	44	4	observation time of first frame in s since 1988.0
13	48	4	observation time of last frame in s since 1988.0
14	52	4	= 0 *** reserved for future use ***
15	56	4	number of attitude records in the file

Data blocksBlock header record

Word	Off	Len	Description
1	0	4	= 2 number of words in this block header record
2	4	4	number of records in this block

True attitude record

Name	Off	Len	Description
FMTIME	0	4	frame mid-time in s since 1988.0
	4	4	micro-seconds part of the frame mid-time
TRANGL	8	4	true revolving angle a [rad] stored as $\text{int}(a*2^{**}24)$ where a is in the range 0 to 2π
	12	4	remaining part ra of revolving angle stored as: $\text{nint}(ra*2^{**}24)$ where $ra = a*2^{**}24 - \text{int}(a*2^{**}24)$
TRPHAS	16	4	true revolving phase p [rad] stored as: $\text{int}(p*2^{**}24)$ where p is in the range 0 to 2π
	20	4	remaining part rp of revolving phase stored as: $\text{nint}(rp*2^{**}24)$ where $rp = p*2^{**}24 - \text{int}(p*2^{**}24)$
TSPHAS	24	4	true spin phase s [rad] stored as: $\text{int}(s*2^{**}24)$ where s is in the range 0 to 2π
	28	4	remaining part rs of spin phase stored as: $\text{nint}(rs*2^{**}24)$ where $rs = s*2^{**}24 - \text{int}(s*2^{**}24)$